

Synthesis of 3-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-4-phenyl-5-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines

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Some 3-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-4-phenyl-5-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (3) have been synthesized for the first time involving interaction of *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloroisothiocarbamoyl chloride (1) and 1-phenyl-3-arylthiocarbamides (2).

The *N*-glucosylated compounds have been known for their great biological importance. They have been found several application in the paper¹, textile^{2,3} and food⁴ industries. Besides these applications, they have been found use as diuretic agents, analgesics, antidiabetic compounds, bacteriostatic agents and in many other ways⁵. Some of them have been found to be valuable oxidation dyes⁶ for printing and padding animal and vegetable fibres by oxidation dyeing methods. Quite a few of them have antitumor and tuberculostatic activity⁷.

We have recently prepared tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate by the interaction of tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl bromide and lead thiocyanate in xylene medium⁸. *N*-Tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloroisothiocarbamoyl chloride (1) have been prepared for the first time by the interaction of tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate with chlorine gas. In view of our interest in *N*-glucosylated cyclic compounds, we now report the synthesis of 3-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-4-phenyl-5-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (3).

Results and discussion

The reaction of *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloroisothiocarbamoyl chloride (1) and 1-phenyl-3-*m*-chlorophenylthiocarbamide (2a) was carried out in cold dry chloroform for 24 h. The solvent chloroform was distilled off and sticky mass was isolated as residue. This when triturated several times with petroleum ether was converted to a granular yellow solid (3a) crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 85°. The product was found to desulfurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. The specific rotation⁹ was found to be $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 64.10$ (*c*, 0.312 in CHCl₃). The purity of products was check by TLC¹⁰ silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ and recorded *R_f* value 0.69. Its IR spectrum¹¹⁻¹⁶ revealed bands at ν_{\max} 3065.8 (Ar-H), 2928.4 (C-H), 1729.6 (C=O),

1593.0 (S=C=N), 1544.5 (N=C=N), 1353.7 (C-N), 1269.4 (C-O), 1092 (C-Cl), 865.7 (glucopyranosyl ring deformation), 751.9 (C-S), 709.0 (monosubstituted ring), 502.0 cm⁻¹ (S-S). Its ¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃)^{11,12,17} displayed signals due to aromatic protons 7.0-8.25 (m), pyranosyl ring protons were located at 4.4-5.9 (m) and CH₂-O proton at 3.4-3.8. In its mass spectrum the molecular ion peak at M⁺ 897 was located along with other fragment peaks¹⁸⁻²⁰ at *m/z* (rel. abundance) 886 (12.5), 860 (26.2), 824 (48.5), 790 (18.6), 765 (42.0), 748 (25.0), 731 (12.0), 706 (22.0), 684 (35.0), 579 (82.5), 390 (27.0), 356 (93.0), 322 (100), 231 (32.5), 105 (100).

where, R = (s) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *m*-tolyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *p*-tolyl, (g) phenyl.

Bz = Benzoyl (-CO-C₆H₅)

Scheme 1

On the basis of all the above facts, the product with m.p. 85° was assigned structure 3-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-4-phenyl-5-*m*-chlorophenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (**3a**).

The reaction of *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloroisothiocarbamoyl chloride was extended to several other substituted thiocarbamides and the corresponding products (**3b-g**) were isolated (Table 1).

Table 1. 3-Tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-4-phenyl-5-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (**3**)

Compd.	Compd.	M.p.	Yield	$[\alpha]_D^{28}$ in CHCl ₃	<i>R_f</i>
(g)	(g)	°C	%		
2a (1.3)	3a (3.0)	85	66.88	+ 64.10 (c, 0.312)	0.69
2b (1.3)	3b (3.5)	94	79.48	+ 98.36 (c, 0.244)	0.62
2c (1.3)	3c (3.9)	110	86.95	+ 90.57 (c, 0.276)	0.42
2d (1.2)	3d (2.0)	120	50.56	+ 120.9 (c, 0.248)	0.71
2e (1.2)	3e (4.0)	75	91.20	- 73.52 (c, 0.272)	0.59
2f (1.2)	3f (1.4)	179	32.55	- 108.69 (c, 0.276)	0.80
2g (1.1)	3g (2.7)	165	62.57	- 43.10 (c, 0.232)	0.82

Satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses found in all cases.

Experimental

The required *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloroisothiocarbamoyl chloride^{21,22} (**1**) and 1-phenyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides (**2a-g**) were prepared by the known method.

*3-Tetra-O-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-4-phenyl-5-*m*-chlorophenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3a)*: A chloroformic solution of *N*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-*S*-chloroisothiocarbamoyl chloride (0.005 *M*, 3.5 g) is mixed with chloroformic solution of 1-phenyl-3-*m*-chlorophenyl thiocarbamide (0.005 *M*, 1.3 g). The mixture was shaken for a few minutes. The clear solution kept for 24 h in ice cold condition. Chloroform was then removed by distillation and the resultant syrupy mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80°). When a yellowish solid (3.0 g) was obtained which was crystallised from ethanol water (**3a**), m.p. 85° (Found: N, 4.95, S, 7.63. C₄₈H₃₆H₉N₃S₂Cl calcd. for: N, 4.68, S, 7.13%).

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References

- H. W. J. J. Meijer, U. S. Pat., 259268/1952 (*Chem. Abst.*, 1952, **46**, 10636).
- H. W. J. J. Meijer, U. S. Pat., 2612497/1952 (*Chem. Abst.*, 1953, **47**, 1402).
- K. Quehl, U. S. Pat., 2116640/1938 (*Chem. Abst.*, 1938, **32**, 500).
- J. J. Opplt, U. S. Pat., 2694719/1954 (*Chem. Abst.*, 1955, **49**, 2639).
- Irving Goodman, "Advances in Carbohydrate Chemistry", New York, 1958, **13**, 233.
- K. Weis, O. Bayer and Kleiner, Ger. Pat., 1011849/1957 (*Chem. Abst.*, 1960, **54**, 9312).
- M. Tomoya, N. Shigeru, K. Kazuo and S. Tetsuo, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1975, **48**, 3763 (*Chem. Abst.*, 1976, **84**, 90463).
- G. V. Korpe and S. P. Deshmukh, *Oriental J. Chem.*, 2001, **17**, 307.
- Arnold Weissberger, "Physical Methods of Organic Chemistry", 2nd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1949, Part II.
- B. Fried and S. H. Sherma, "Thin-Layer Chromatography", 2nd. ed., Chromatographic Science Series, Dekker, New York, 1986, 35.
- R. M. Silverstein, G. C. Bassler and T. C. Morrill, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 5th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1991.
- J. R. Dyer, "Application of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice-Hall, New York, 1974.
- N. B. Colthup, L. H. Daly and S. E. Wiberley, "Introduction of Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1964.
- S. A. Barker, E. J. Bourne, R. Stephens and D. H. Whiffen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3468.
- Margareta Avram and G. H. Matescu, "Infrared Spectroscopy Applications in Organic Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1970.
- Jose Fuentes, Wenceslao Moreda, Carmen Ortiz, Immaculada Robina and Colin Welsh, *Tetrahedron*, 1992, **48**, 6413.
- S. A. Barker, J. Homen, M. C. Keith and L. F. Thomas, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1538.
- Norma B. D. Accorso and Inge M. E. Thiel, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1984, **129**, 43.
- K. Biemann, D. C. Dejongh and H. K. Schnoes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1763.
- H. Budzikiewicz, C. Djerassi and D. H. Williams, "Structural Elucidation of Natural products by Mass Spectrometry", II, Holden Day, 1964, p. 207.
- G. Ottmann and H. Hooks, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 838.
- M. G. Paranjpe and A. S. Mahajan, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 1138.